

1 **Polypyrimidine tract binding protein 2 (PTBP2) functions together with Xist in transcriptional**
2 **control.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We used proteomic and transcriptomic approaches to identifying the full complement of Xist interacting
8 partners for discovery and complete characterization of Xist functions. We describe here a function for the
9 Xist non-coding RNA that involves interaction with the polypyrimidine tract binding protein 2 (*Ptbp2*).

10 Citations

11 1. Licatalosi, D.D., Yano, M., Fak, J.J., Mele, A., Grabinski, S.E., Zhang, C. and Darnell, R.B., 2012.
12 *Ptbp2* represses adult-specific splicing to regulate the generation of neuronal precursors in the embryonic
13 brain. *Genes & development*, 26(14), pp.1626-1642.

14 2. Hannigan, M.M., Zagore, L.L. and Licatalosi, D.D., 2017. *Ptbp2* controls an alternative splicing
15 network required for cell communication during spermatogenesis. *Cell reports*, 19(12), pp.2598-2612.

16 3. Zagore, L.L., Grabinski, S.E., Sweet, T.J., Hannigan, M.M., Sramkoski, R.M., Li, Q. and Licatalosi,
17 D.D., 2015. RNA binding protein *Ptbp2* is essential for male germ cell development. *Molecular and cellular*
18 *biology*, 35(23), pp.4030-4042.

19 4. Ling, J.P., Chhabra, R., Merran, J.D., Schaughency, P.M., Wheelan, S.J., Corden, J.L. and Wong,
20 P.C., 2016. PTBP1 and PTBP2 repress nonconserved cryptic exons. *Cell reports*, 17(1), pp.104-113.

21 5. Vuong, J.K., Lin, C.H., Zhang, M., Chen, L., Black, D.L. and Zheng, S., 2016. PTBP1 and PTBP2
22 serve both specific and redundant functions in neuronal pre-mRNA splicing. *Cell reports*, 17(10),
23 pp.2766-2775.
24
25
26
27
28